

FEATURES OF ATTENTION DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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Abstract. *This article examines the features of attention development in children with speech disorders, since attention is an important factor in the child's cognitive activity and its organization, as well as the low level of voluntary attention, difficulties in concentrating and distributing attention, difficulties in planning and controlling one's own activities, and difficulties in focusing attention on speech material.*

Keywords: *speech therapy, attention, child with speech disorders, psychological research, cognitive activity, instability, voluntary attention, corrective effect.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, one of the main directions in speech therapy is the comprehensive psychological and pedagogical study of children with developmental disorders. This direction is especially relevant in preschool speech therapy, since it is at this age that early identification and elimination of primary and secondary defects allows for the activation of the correctional work process.

In the study of psychological characteristics, voluntary attention is of great importance as an important factor in the child's cognitive activity and its organization. Attention is the concentration of consciousness on a specific real or imaginary object, which includes the enhancement of the individual's sensory, intellectual, or motor activity. By origin and method of influence, attention is divided into two main types: voluntary and involuntary.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

L.S. Vygotsky demonstrates that the acquisition of continuous speech in the process of object activity and interaction with adults is the acquisition of voluntary attention from them. As a key to the genetic understanding of attention, L.S. Vygotsky sees its roots not in the child's personality, but outside of it. According to Vygotsky, verbal instructions from adults play an extremely important role in the formation of voluntary attention in a child, since the focusing of additional reflexes on specific objects has a fundamental influence on the sign systems of attention [2; 67].

The characteristics of attention in children with speech disorders have been studied by O.N. Usanova, Yu.F. Garkusha, and others. It has been established that attention in children with incomplete speech development is characterized by a number of features: instability, significantly lower indicators of voluntary attention, and difficulties in planning their activities. Children experience difficulties in concentrating attention when analyzing a situation, searching for methods and means of solving problems [1; 23].

It has been established that voluntary attention manifests differently depending on stimuli of different modalities (visual and auditory): children with speech disorders find it much more difficult to concentrate attention when performing tasks with verbal instructions than when performing visual tasks. When performing tasks with verbal instructions, numerous gross deficiencies are observed in distinguishing color, shape, and location of figures. The pace of

activity in preschool children with speech disorders decreases during the work process. For children with speech disorders, the distribution of attention between speech and action is a complex, unattainable task. At the same time, their speech reactions are clarifying and accentuating in nature, and simultaneously, as in children with normal speech development, complex additional effects are observed that are not related to the task being performed simultaneously.

Throughout the work, children with speech disorders experience attention disturbances that are not always independently identified and corrected. The nature of errors and their distribution over time qualitatively differ from the norm [4; 87]. All types of activity control (preparatory, current, and subsequent) are often underdeveloped or significantly impaired, with preparatory and current control (during task performance) often being impaired, which is related to insufficient understanding of the task completion conditions. Final control (control of results), its individual elements, mainly manifest after additional assistance from the teacher: instruction repetition is required, demonstration of an example, specific instructions, etc.

Undoubtedly, the violation of voluntary attention in children with speech defects has been observed by many researchers (R.A. Belova-David), and this category is characterized by the incompleteness and distortion of the general mental development of children [6; 78]. Some scientists see unformed voluntary attention in the study of individual factors of children's mental activity. R.V. Levina notes a violation of voluntary attention in the same activity of three groups of children with speech defects that she identified. Unformed knowledge and, in particular, the inability to independently control their mental activity, according to V.L. Kovshikov and K.A. Elkonin, affect the thinking and results of many children with speech defects. S.N. Shakhovskaya showed that children with speech defects are characterized by rapid fatigue and a low degree of development of various attention characteristics.

Ya.F. Sobatovich believes that fatigue and instability of attention are due to the absence of directing and rapid execution of certain forms of thinking in educational activities. Other scientists study the violation of voluntary attention in the process of analyzing the psycho-organic symptomatology of this category of children. Thus, R.A. Belova-David, studying children with incompletely developed speech, found that instability and narrowing of the sphere of attention, lack of activity and purposefulness, rapid fatigue are the causes of low productivity in all types of mental activity, as well as in speech. G.V. Gurovets divided children with motor alalia into two groups (motor-premotor and motor-central), indicating that both groups have instability of active attention, the first group is characterized by rapid fatigue, and the second by instability [2; 56].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Accordingly, it can be said that children with various speech disorders have a significantly higher level of attention disturbances than healthy children, but these disturbances are determined by individual characteristics.

Analysis of the obtained data shows that indicators of voluntary attention disturbances in children with speech disorders are significantly lower than in children with normal speech development. Experimental data indicate that children with speech disorders require more time to complete most tasks than children with normal speech development. For example, children with motor aphasia completed a visual dictation in 8 minutes 41 seconds (normal - 7 min. 8 sec.), the time required to concentrate attention on completing a task, to attract attention to uninteresting material - 4 minutes 14 seconds (normal - 6 min. 19 sec.). When a similar task was given in game form, the indicators increased: for maximum concentration of attention, children with speech

disorders needed a total of 4 minutes 37 seconds, and children with normal speech development - 7 minutes 24 seconds.

A number of other experimental data also indicate a decrease in voluntary attention in children with speech disorders: children with speech disorders needed 3 minutes to verify the correctness of seen signs, which was 57.1 (normal - 84.1), with an average number of errors made 10.6; the average number of missed signs was 3.5 and 5.8 times more than normal, and when sorting elements by color, the average number of divided elements was 200 (normal - 256), while the average number of errors made by children with speech disorders in this case was 7 times more than in healthy children.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of observations show that children with speech disorders are predominantly characterized by a reproductive type of activity, while children with normal speech development have a productive type of activity. For example, children with speech disorders use the researcher's example when performing construction tasks. Children with normal speech development can independently build more complex structures (trains, houses, etc.), following only the teacher's instructions, while they can comply with the task conditions, if they make mistakes (in color, in the number of parts), find them and correct them. When performing tasks in game form (assembling elements), children with speech disorders use more productive types of work than children with normal speech development, which indicates that their abilities under these conditions rise to a higher level.

The type of instructions given by the researcher affects the concentration of attention of children with speech disorders: under conditions of verbal instructions, the level of task completion is significantly lower. According to the research results, children with speech disorders cannot always accept the tasks given by the researcher; they are characterized by partial, unclear perception of pedagogical instructions, and they perform tasks with various shortcomings. In addition, the study revealed the nature of shortcomings in task performance in children with speech disorders and children with normal speech development over a certain period of time (20 minutes).

If in children with normally developing speech, most errors occur during the period of mastering the target skill (first 5 minutes), then from 10 to 20 minutes errors are rare, whereas in children with speech disorders, errors are observed throughout the entire period of activity, the number of errors slightly decreases in 10-15 minutes when children have mastered the activity skills, and then from 15-20 minutes errors are observed as often as in 1-5 minutes, which indicates a decrease in attention stability in children with speech disorders when fatigued.

One of the important indicators when assessing the level of voluntary attention is the nature of distraction. During the study, the type of distraction in children of the experimental and control groups depends on the level of formation of the activity system. In children with speech disorders, the activity system is either not formed or significantly impaired, which is one of the causes of the low level of development of voluntary attention. For example, if children with normal speech development are characterized by distraction to the researcher (children look at the researcher and, based on their reaction, try to determine whether they are performing the task correctly or incorrectly), then in children with speech disorders, such distraction manifests as follows: "looks in the mirror (in all directions)," "performs actions not related to task completion," etc.

Observations have shown that when teaching children with speech disorders, a gradual increase in the complexity of tasks is very effective, and this category of children needs more quantitative and qualitative assistance from the researcher than healthy children.

Thus, based on the analysis of the results of various studies, conclusions can be drawn about the characteristics of attention in children with speech disorders (Fig. 1).

Features of attention in speech disorders

- instability;
- low level of voluntary attention;
- difficulties with concentration and distribution of attention;
- difficulties in planning and controlling one's own activities;
- difficulties in focusing attention on speech material.

Fig. 1. Characteristics of attention in children with speech disorders.

In children with speech disorders, quantitative indicators of voluntary attention characteristics are significantly lower than in children with normally developed speech. Children with speech disorders are characterized by low reproductive (normally productive) activity and low tactical activity. In game conditions, children with speech disorders use more productive tactical activity than healthy children, which indicates a high level of development of their abilities under these conditions. Differences in the nature of attention distraction in children are related to the formation of the activity system. Violation of voluntary attention leads to the absence of formation or, to a significant extent, to the violation of activity as an important factor in the organization of activities.

In this case, shortcomings are observed in all spheres of activity:

a) children perceive instructions incorrectly and incoherently; it is extremely difficult for them to concentrate attention on analyzing the conditions of the task and finding methods and means for its completion; it is known that children with speech disorders do not use speech to clarify instructions;

b) children perform tasks with errors, the nature of these errors and their distribution over time qualitatively differ from the norm;

c) all types of control (preparatory, current, and subsequent) are considered unformed or significantly impaired, with preparatory and current types of control suffering the most.

One of the effective ways to form voluntary attention in children with speech disorders is its systematic development in the process of activity, taking into account the peculiarities of attention disturbances in this category of children and the development of other higher mental functions.

CONCLUSION

Speech activity is a systematic process that includes verbal and non-verbal components. Their unity is determined by a number of factors, primarily the type and form of speech, as well as non-verbal activity, the nature of the speech communication situation, practical or intellectual tasks. Under conditions of speech dysontogenesis, the child's higher mental activity and emotional-volitional sphere develop in a specific way. Insufficient formation of speech and complex interaction of cognitive functions are observed.

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